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Testing of new blade materials for marine energy converters using a reference model turbine in the UNH towing tank

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Abstract

A design team at the University of Illinois has engineered bio-inspired sandwich-like layered composite systems for use in marine turbines. Turbines with blades made from these materials will be tested in the University of New Hampshire (UNH) Towing Tank using a reference model turbine at the 1-meter scale. The reference model will be a three-bladed cross-flow turbine with straight NACA 0020 blades, referred to as the UNH-Reference Vertical Axis Turbine (UNH-RVAT). Alternatively, a cross-flow reference model turbine with tapering NACA 0021 blades, referred to as the DOE-Sandia Reference Model 2 (RM2) turbine at 1:6 scale can also be used. The main goal of the experiments will be to quantify the relative performance of the new blades with each other and with the reference material, Al 6061-T6. This contribution will report on the experiment design.

Keywords: Tidal Energy; River Current; Laboratory testing; Bio-inspired materials

1. Introduction

When designing a marine or riverine current turbine, the material of the blades can affect the performance of the turbine as well as the mechanical loads it can withstand [1].

The team at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign is creating blade sets with three unique material combinations, the first being a novel fiber-reinforced polymer composite, second being a polymer composite/wood layered system, and third being a steel/polymer composite/wood layered system. This approach was chosen because the layered structure allows for high turbulence and mechanical loads. Different materials will be tested and selected based on the best combination of performance, durability, and lifecycle cost.

These new blade materials will then be tested at the UNH tow tank testing facility, where the blades will be attached to an existing turbine test bed and shaft. The new blades will be tested for varying Reynolds numbers and under different inflow conditions to see how the materials compare to the existing blades made from Al 6061-T6. Results will be analyzed to compare performance for the different blade sets.

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Nomenclature	
ADV	Acoustic Doppler velocimeter
FBG	Fiber Bragg Grating
RM2	Reference Model 2
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
TSR	Tip speed ratio, $\lambda = \omega R/U_\infty$
UNH-RVAT	University of New Hampshire Reference Vertical-Axis Turbine
Re_D	Reynolds number based on free stream speed and turbine diameter, $Re_D = U_\infty D/\nu$
$Re_{c,avg}$	Reynolds number based on average relative velocity and blade chord, $Re_{c,avg} = \lambda U_\infty c/\nu$
c	Blade chord length
$C_{p,max}$	Power coefficient maximum
D	Turbine diameter
R	Turbine radius
ν	Water viscosity
ω	Angular velocity

2. Experimental design

The testing of the turbines with new blade materials will be conducted in the UNH tow tank, which is 12 ft wide, 8 ft deep, and 120 ft long. The tank consists of a tow carriage, which rides on case-hardened Thomson rails, driven by a 30 hp servo motor via an endless toothed belt. The UNH Tow and Wave Tank enables research where test bodies can be towed, subjected to wave action, or both. A tow tank provides a clean uniform inflow, which is useful for turbine performance evaluation, wake measurements, and numerical model validation. To test with a turbulent inflow, a turbulence generating grid or other turbulence-generating structures such as vertical pipes, can be mounted on the carriage upstream of the turbine under test.

The tow system provides highly accurate control of acceleration, velocity, and position. A low drag, 2nd generation hydrokinetic turbine test bed, with a submerged frame made from extruded aluminum NACA 0020 struts with 140 mm chord, is used to test cross-flow turbines up to nominally 1 square meter cross-section. This allows turbine models of a size where performance becomes independent of Reynolds number while maintaining reasonable blockage. The UNH turbine test bed was developed to allow for testing to be done according to international marine energy specifications: IEC TS 62600-202, *Marine energy - Wave, tidal and other water current converters - Part 202: Early stage development of tidal energy converters - Best practices and recommended procedures for the testing of pre-prototype scale device* (published 2022) [2].

Turbine torque, angular velocity, and thrust measurements

The tow tank carriage is outfitted with several instruments to measure torque, angular velocity, and thrust. Torque is measured by an Interface T8-200 torque transducer with a nominal accuracy of ± 0.5 Nm, as well as a redundant torque arm which is a Sentran ZB3-200 load cell with a nominal accuracy of ± 0.2 Nm. The turbine rotor is controlled by a Kollmorgen AKM62Q servo motor with 10^5 pulse/revolution resolution. The turbine shaft angle is measured using the encoder output from the AKM62Q, which can be converted to the turbine angular velocity. The test bed is supported by linear bearings and connected to two S-beam load cells to measure overall system thrust. This setup uses two Sentran ZB3-500 load cells with accuracy ± 0.6 N, and there is one load cell on each side of the carriage to measure left and right thrust.

There will first be baseline testing conducted, where the turbine will be tested using its original blades made of Al 6061-T6. These tests require a tare drag test, where the turbine test bed frame is towed without a turbine in the tow tank over the same range of towing speeds run during later testing. This allows for the mean thrust value of the test bed to be subtracted in data processing to estimate the rotor thrust by itself.

Similarly, tare torque tests will be performed by rotating the turbine shaft in air without turbine blades, over the range of angular velocities used in later testing. These torque values will then be fit with a linear regression and added to the turbine torque during data processing.

Fig. 1. Tare drag/thrust testing with the cross-flow turbine test bed being conducted in the UNH tow tank.

2.1. Baseline experiments

Baseline tests will be conducted using either the UNH-RVAT or RM2 turbine with the original aluminum blades. The UNH-RVAT has a 1.0 m diameter and is made of NACA 0020 blades with a chord length of 0.14 m, giving a chord to radius ratio $c/R=0.28$ [3]. The RM2 turbine is a 1.08 m diameter turbine with tapered NACA 0021 blades. The chord ranges from 0.040-0.067 m and the chord-to-radius ratio varies from $c/R=0.07$ -0.12 [4]. Both turbines can be seen in Figure 2.

Turbine performance curves will be established for varying tip speed ratios, $\lambda = \omega R/U_\infty$, and increasing tow speeds, U_∞ , to determine above which Reynolds number (Re) turbine performance becomes Re -independent. All further testing will then be conducted at tow speeds that exceed this critical Reynolds number, to eliminate Reynolds number as a parameter.

Reynolds number can be calculated based either on turbine diameter or average blade chord. To compare power performance with Reynolds number based on turbine diameter, the following definition would be used:

$$Re_D = \frac{U_\infty D}{\nu} \quad (1)$$

Here U_∞ is the freestream (in this case, tow carriage) velocity, D is the turbine diameter, and ν is the water kinematic viscosity. The Reynolds number based on average relative velocity and blade chord is defined as:

$$Re_{c,avg} = \frac{\lambda U_\infty c}{\nu} \quad (2)$$

Here λ is tip speed ratio and c is blade chord length. The turbine performance curve will asymptote to a Reynolds number independent curve with a peak performance value, $C_{p,max}$, at a specific tip speed ratio λ , which is the turbine operating point where further testing should focus.

Fig. 2. (a) UNH-RVAT turbine with NACA 0020 blades (b) RM2 turbine with tapered NACA 0021 blades.

2.2. Bio-inspired blade experiments

Using a layered material structure will allow a turbine to withstand higher mechanical loads and turbulence values than typical design requirements. The proposed utilization of aromatic thermosetting copolyesters (ATSP) in these blades would allow for very low moisture absorption, excellent mechanical properties, and can be used in different forms, such as a coating or foam [5]. These properties make this material well suited for a marine turbine application.

The design of these blades will be bio-inspired, meaning it will be based on nature-based structures, such as bones and shells. These structures are naturally built to prevent damages, using an outer shell to protect from fracture and an inner porous material to absorb loadings [6]. These ideas will be incorporated into the layered design of these high-performance blades using a combination of the ATSP material with other material systems, such as wood and steel. Up to three different blade sets with differing material combinations may be manufactured.

After the baseline tests are complete, the bio-inspired blades will be put through the same testing, varying tow speeds and tip speed ratio to find the Re-independent range. While one may expect that turbines of the same geometry should exhibit the same Reynolds number dependence, this may vary if the blade deforms significantly [1]. Once testing is complete, the performance of the bio-inspired blades will be compared to that of the aluminum blades to see how the new materials compare with the original blades.

In addition to the measurements collected by the UNH tow tank carriage, blade strain measurements can be taken using Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors imbedded in the turbine blades. These measurements will show the deflection of the blade and can give more insight to the performance of the blades during testing.

2.3. Turbine testing under turbulent inflow conditions

Once all of the blades have been tested under regular conditions (i.e. non-turbulent), all of the blade sets will then be tested within the same parameters as the previous tests, but with turbulent inflow conditions. Turbulence will be created from a turbulence generating structure being mounted upstream of the turbine on the tow carriage. This structure can either be a turbulence generating grid or cylinder. The current turbulence grid available for the UNH tow tank has a 2.5 inch mesh width and will have average turbulence intensities measured to be about 23% at 5 mesh widths downstream of the grid [7]. This results in a solidity of 0.36, which is the lowest that will produce isotropic homogeneous turbulence [8].

The turbulence will be characterized using an acoustic Doppler velocimeter (ADV). The tow tank will be seeded with very small hollow glass spheres to scatter sound and obtain acceptable signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in the ADV. Once the ADV is set up and reading properly, the turbine will be tested within the Re-independent range. The

performance of the turbine in the turbulent conditions will be compared with the results from the previous, non-turbulent tests.

3. Summary

This study will investigate the effect of novel, bio-inspired materials on the performance of a 1.0m scale marine cross-flow turbine within a Reynolds number independent regime in the UNH Towing Tank. The performance of the bio-inspired blades will be compared to that of the original aluminum blades of either the UNH-RVAT or RM2 turbine in both undisturbed and turbulent inflow. The results will give insight into the effectiveness of new materials in a marine and riverine energy converter application.

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